

The psychological impact of Internet Gaming Disorder on adolescents and young Adults in India

Rizwana Farween Rajmohamed & Evangeline Supriya
JAIN University (India)

dr.rizwana0a@gmail.com

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Publication of the International Society of Psychology, Counselling and Education

Gaming is a widely popular activity among adolescents, but excessive gaming can lead to gaming disorder, now recognised as a psychiatric condition in ICD-11 and DSM-5. While most research on gaming behaviour has focused on Western and North Asian populations, this study examines its prevalence and psychological effects among Indian adolescents. The study recruited 150 participants via online gaming communities and assessed their gaming habits, frequency, addiction levels, and daily emotional states through self-report questionnaires. Results indicated that 6% of participants met the criteria for gaming addiction. Correlational analysis revealed significant associations between gaming disorder scores and psychological variables, with emotional symptoms, conduct issues, antisocial behaviour, and peer problems showing positive correlations, while hyperactivity scores were negatively correlated. A Mann–Whitney U-test identified significant differences between participants with and without gaming disorder in emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity/inattention, and peer difficulties. These findings highlight key psychopathological traits associated with gaming addiction, supporting early screening and prevention efforts in India.

Keywords: addiction; adolescence; emotional regulation; online gaming; psychopathology

In the modern technological era, internet usage has become an integral aspect of daily life. The rapid growth of technology and innovation in recent decades has significantly influenced gaming activities. Before the advent of the internet, teenagers and young adults primarily engaged in offline games, which fostered social connections and contributed to emotional maturity and psychological well-being. However, the landscape of entertainment has shifted dramatically, with online and console gaming becoming the preferred mode of engagement. Video gaming has emerged as a widely popular leisure activity among adults, with the average weekly playtime in South Asia increasing from 5.1 hours in 2011 to 6.5 hours in 2017. In the modern technological era, internet usage has become an integral aspect of daily life. The rapid growth of technology and innovation in recent decades has significantly influenced gaming activities. Before the advent of the internet, teenagers and young adults primarily engaged in offline games, which fostered social connections and contributed to emotional maturity and psychological well-being. However, the landscape of entertainment has shifted dramatically, with online and console gaming becoming the preferred mode of engagement. Video gaming has emerged as a widely popular leisure activity among adults, with the average weekly playtime in South Asia increasing from 5.1 hours in 2011 to 6.5 hours in 2017.

A video game is defined as a game which we play thanks to an audio-visual apparatus and which can be based on a story. In recent years, scientific research on video game playing has expanded considerably. While some studies highlight the benefits of gaming, such as improved focus, multitasking abilities, and working memory, others have raised concerns about its potential dangers. Although some research suggests that online gaming facilitates entertainment and social connections, a significant body of literature underscores its negative implications. The debate regarding whether the effects of video gaming are beneficial or harmful continues, but with the rapid advancement of online gaming, concerns about its potential to become problematic – especially among teenagers – are growing. Online video games are increasingly associated with addictive behaviour, and excessive gaming poses potential risks to psychological well-being, as indicated by numerous studies. Over the years, considerable research has been devoted to understanding gaming patterns, behaviour, and their implications for mental health, particularly from psychiatric and psychosocial perspectives. A significant proportion of the existing literature suggests that online gaming influences psychological well-being. While research on online and offline gaming behaviour and its associated challenges dates back to the 1990s, concerns surrounding problematic gaming have only recently been formally recognised and given clinical significance.

Addiction, which involves the compulsive engagement with a substance or activity despite negative consequences, is central to addictive disorders. It is characterised by dependence, tolerance, and withdrawal symptoms. Addiction can be classified into physical and psychological dependence. Physical dependence occurs when frequent use of a substance results in withdrawal symptoms upon cessation, whereas psychological dependence involves an emotional compulsion to engage in behaviour without a physical requirement. For instance, individuals who quit smoking may recover physically in a short period, yet their emotional craving for nicotine persists for much longer. Tolerance develops when repeated exposure to a substance results in diminished effects, necessitating an increased dosage to achieve the same response. This phenomenon occurs with various substances, including legally prescribed medications such as benzodiazepines (e.g., Valium) and illicit drugs like cocaine. While tolerance does not inherently indicate addiction, it contributes to dependence. The severity of tolerance varies depending on the substance's effects. For example, individual using cocaine may need progressively larger doses to attain euphoric sensations, yet this escalation increases the risk of severe respiratory complications and fatal outcomes. Withdrawal symptoms arise when an individual with a dependency on drugs or alcohol ceases or reduces usage. Since the brain adapts its function to the presence of the substance, its absence disrupts

equilibrium, triggering intense psychological symptoms such as depression, anxiety, and irritability, alongside physical effects like nausea, insomnia, and weight loss. The severity of withdrawal symptoms varies according to the substance type, dosage, and duration of use. The anticipation of these distressing symptoms often reinforces continued substance use (Relajo-Howell et al., 2024).

Although internet gaming was initially developed as a form of entertainment with recommended time limitations, its addictive nature has raised considerable concerns among adolescents and young adults. Similar to substance addiction, excessive gaming has been linked to psychological issues such as anxiety, social withdrawal, and interpersonal difficulties. Spending excessive amounts of time gaming during childhood and adolescence – critical periods for personal development and education – may lead to social isolation and psychiatric disorders in adulthood. Of greater concern is the classification of excessive gaming behaviour as a mental health disorder, with specific diagnostic criteria under the term Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD). The extent to which this condition affects individuals remains unclear, necessitating further research to determine its prevalence within different populations. This study aims to assess the prevalence of IGD among Indian video game players and to examine its associations with various psychological variables, including emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity and attention deficit issues, peer relationship difficulties, and prosocial behaviour.

There is currently limited research analysing the prevalence of IGD within the Indian population, despite India having the second-largest adolescent and young adult demographic globally and a rapidly growing gaming industry. Notably, India has been largely excluded from major global meta-analyses on IGD prevalence. This research seeks to bridge this gap by focusing on internet gaming addiction and its psychological effects among Indian gamers. While extensive research exists on substance addiction, studies on non-substance addictions remain limited (Sinclair et al., 2021). This gap is particularly concerning given the rapid advancement of technology and the widespread popularity of internet gaming among adolescents. Despite its inclusion in the DSM-5 as a recognised mental condition, internet gaming disorder remains understudied in psychological research. The increasing focus on adolescent mental health makes it essential to evaluate whether excessive gaming warrants classification as a mental disorder. Addressing this gap is crucial, underscoring the need for this study. The study, therefore, investigates the prevalence of Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD) among young adults and examines its psychological, social, and behavioural effects in the Indian context. The objectives of the study are to assess the trends and patterns of internet gaming activities among young adults in India and to evaluate the behavioural, social, and psychological effects of gaming among young players in India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD) has expanded significantly over the past decade, with multiple studies examining its prevalence, psychological correlates, and underlying mechanisms. Global prevalence estimates of IGD vary widely, largely due to differences in assessment methods, cultural factors, and sample populations. A meta-analysis assessing IGD prevalence from 2009 to 2019 across 17 countries, primarily in Europe, reported a global prevalence of 3.05%, with a higher incidence among adolescents and young adults compared to older individuals (Stevens et al., 2021). Males were found to be significantly more affected than females. Another global prevalence study in 2020 found that IGD rates ranged from 0.21% to 58% in general populations and 3.20% to 91% in clinical populations, with a higher prevalence in Asian countries (Undavalli et al., 2020). However, data for the South-East Asian region remains limited, highlighting a gap in research. Within the Indian context, IGD prevalence among school, undergraduate, and postgraduate students has been reported to range from 1.3% to 19.9% for adolescents and 4% for young adults, with a higher incidence in male gamers. The COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated concerns, as physical

restrictions and reduced real-world interactions contributed to increased gaming activity, potentially heightening the risk for IGD.

Beyond prevalence rates, researchers have investigated psychological mechanisms underlying problematic gaming behaviour. Gaming is often used as a coping strategy for emotional distress, which may lead to maladaptive gaming patterns. Reinecke (2009) explored the relationship between stress exposure and gaming frequency in a sample of German gamers and found that individuals who relied on emotion-focused coping strategies were more likely to use gaming as an escape, reinforcing the notion that gaming can serve as a form of psychological avoidance. Estevez et al. (2019) further examined coping strategies within the framework of attachment theory, demonstrating that individuals with avoidant coping styles and self-blame tendencies were at a higher risk for problematic gaming. These findings suggest that individuals with difficulties regulating emotions may be more vulnerable to gaming-related behavioural addictions, a hypothesis supported by neurobiological research. Shin et al. (2021) investigated the neural mechanisms associated with problematic video gaming, highlighting increased activation in brain regions linked to impulsivity and emotion dysregulation among individuals with IGD. These findings align with earlier work by Kim et al. (2022), who examined neurobiological similarities between IGD and substance use disorders. Using positron emission tomography (PET) scans, their study found that both IGD and alcohol use disorder patients exhibited reduced functional connectivity in multiple brain regions, suggesting potential overlaps in addiction-related neurocircuitry. These findings support the classification of IGD as a behavioural addiction, although further research is needed to determine whether problematic gaming represents a distinct disorder or a symptom of broader psychological vulnerabilities.

The psychological consequences of problematic gaming extend beyond emotional regulation difficulties to include social and behavioural challenges. Ansari and Patel investigated the association between violent video game exposure and social outcomes, finding that individuals who engaged in violent gaming exhibited higher levels of peer problems, temper outbursts, and social anxiety compared to those who played non-violent games. Similarly, Huang et al. (2022) examined the relationship between IGD and anxiety symptoms among children and adolescents in China, concluding that anxiety was a significant predictor of IGD severity. These findings are consistent with studies on other forms of behavioural addiction, such as the work of Mallik et al. (2021), which demonstrated that psychological inflexibility and reduced mindfulness were associated with stronger cravings in substance-related disorders.

A growing body of research suggests that problematic gaming is linked not only to emotional distress but also to social isolation. von der Heiden et al. (2019) examined gaming behaviours in a large-scale study of 2,891 German university students, revealing that problematic gaming was associated with increased social withdrawal, poor academic performance, and heightened emotional distress. In contrast, some gamers reported that video games provided positive emotions and social interactions, suggesting that gaming motivations and game genres play a critical role in determining whether gaming has a beneficial or maladaptive impact on psychological well-being. These findings underscore the importance of distinguishing between recreational and problematic gaming, as not all individuals who engage in frequent gaming exhibit signs of addiction or psychological distress.

The association between problematic gaming and social relationships has been further explored in cross-cultural studies. Travaglino et al. (2020) found that individuals who identified strongly as “gamers” were more likely to exhibit problematic gaming tendencies, particularly when their primary source of social support came from online gaming communities rather than real-world relationships. Similarly, Cudo et al. (2019) investigated self-esteem, loneliness, and self-efficacy as predictors of problematic gaming and found that males who reported high levels of loneliness and

low self-esteem were more likely to engage in excessive gaming. However, this relationship was not observed in females, suggesting that gender differences may moderate the psychological impact of problematic gaming. Moreover, the role of maladaptive coping and escapism in problematic gaming has also been well documented. Plante et al. (2019) found that individuals who used video games as a primary coping mechanism for stress and anxiety exhibited higher levels of gaming addiction symptoms. Similarly, Blasi et al. (2019) explored the concept of escapism in massively multiplayer online role-playing games (MMORPGs), demonstrating that individuals who engaged in avoidance-based gaming exhibited greater emotion dysregulation and problematic gaming behaviours. These findings suggest that problematic gaming may serve as a maladaptive coping strategy for underlying psychological distress, rather than being an inherently harmful activity in itself.

While the classification of Internet Gaming Disorder remains a topic of debate, existing research consistently highlights its association with psychological distress, social difficulties, and maladaptive coping mechanisms. The evidence suggests that problematic gaming is not merely a consequence of excessive screen time but is often intertwined with broader emotional and social vulnerabilities. Given the growing prevalence of online gaming, particularly among adolescents and young adults, further research is needed to explore risk factors, protective mechanisms, and potential intervention strategies. Longitudinal studies would be particularly valuable in assessing the long-term impact of gaming behaviours on psychological well-being and distinguishing between healthy gaming habits and gaming-related psychopathology.

METHODOLOGY

This study aims to test two primary hypotheses. First, the Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD) score will be higher among game players than non-game players in India. Second, game players with high IGD scores will exhibit a greater degree of hyperactivity, prosocial behaviour, and emotional distress, conduct problems, and peer relationship issues. The independent variables in this study include the Internet Gaming Disorder score and the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) total score, along with subscale scores measuring emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity, peer relationship problems, and prosocial behaviour. The dependent variables include the distinction between internet game players and non-internet game players, gender differences among players, and gaming frequency and duration.

Participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Individuals aged 15 and above who engage in online or offline video gaming was included in the study, along with those who do not play video games. Participants with a history of medical, physical, or psychological disorders were excluded, as were those under the age of 15 and individuals who only watch others play video games rather than playing themselves.

A correlational quantitative research design was employed, and data were collected through an online questionnaire distributed between 01 May and 01 June 2024. The study recruited 150 adolescents and young adults from southern India, specifically from Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Karnataka, using a random convenience sampling method. The questionnaire was primarily shared on social media platforms and gaming forums to ensure a higher representation of gamers. No remuneration or incentives were offered, and participants were informed of this prior to participation.

Before completing the questionnaire, participants were provided with a brief description outlining the study's purpose. The survey was designed to include both gamers and non-gamers, ensuring a diverse participant pool. Participants were informed about potential minimal risks, data protection policies, and confidentiality measures. After providing informed consent, participants completed a

series of questionnaires assessing gaming activities, psychological well-being, social connections, and potential problematic gaming behaviour. A demographic section gathered information such as age, gender, locality, gaming frequency, and gaming duration. To maintain anonymity, participants were instructed not to provide any personal identifiers. Upon completing the survey, they received a thank-you note, along with an online self-help resource for gaming addiction.

Participants provided socio-demographic data, including age, gender, locality, gaming frequency per week and per day, gaming duration, and preferred gaming platform. The study utilised validated instruments to measure psychological variables quantitatively. The Internet Gaming Disorder Scale – Short Form (IGDS9-SF), developed by Pontes and Griffiths (2015), was used to assess IGD symptoms such as withdrawal, obsession, tolerance, and mood alteration based on DSM-5 criteria. The nine-item scale required participants to rate their agreement on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from never to very often. A total score above 32 indicated a high likelihood of IGD. The scale demonstrated strong internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.86 in this study.

In addition to the IGDS9-SF, the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) developed by Goodman (2001) was employed to assess emotional and behavioural problems. The SDQ consists of five subscales: emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity and attention deficit, peer relationship problems, and prosocial behaviour. Each subscale comprises five items rated on a three-point Likert scale. Higher scores indicate greater psychological difficulty, except in the prosocial behaviour subscale, where a higher score denotes positive attributes. The SDQ demonstrated acceptable reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.694 in this study.

The study adhered to ethical research principles, including voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw at any stage. Participants were assured that their responses would be used solely for research purposes and that their identities would remain anonymous. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board before data collection commenced.

DATA ANALYSIS

A total of 154 individuals participated in the study. However, four questionnaires were incomplete and were excluded from the analysis, resulting in a final sample size of 150 participants. The respondents were from the southern states of India, including Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, and Telangana.

The responses from the electronic questionnaire were exported to Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarise the socio-demographic data. For continuous variables, the mean (*M*) and standard deviation (*SD*) were calculated, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. To examine relationships between variables, the Spearman correlation test was used to assess associations between the total IGDS9-SF score and the total and subscale scores of the SDQ. The magnitude of correlation was interpreted based on the Pearson correlation coefficient (*r*), where values between 0.01 and 0.09 indicated negligible correlation, 0.1 to 0.29 denoted low correlation, 0.3 to 0.49 represented moderate correlation, 0.5 to 0.69 showed substantial correlation, and values greater than 0.7 indicated a very strong correlation.

To further investigate group differences, the Mann-Whitney U-test was performed to compare scores on all dependent variables and determine the significance of correlations between them. This non-parametric test was chosen due to the potential non-normal distribution of the data, allowing for a robust comparison of differences between independent groups.

RESULTS

Table 1
 Descriptive statistics of socio-demographic characteristics (*n* = 50)

Age categories	
15–17	12 (8%)
18–20	21 (14%)
21–25	30 (20%)
26–30	75 (50%)
31–35	12 (8%)
>35	0
Gender	
Male	85 (56.6%)
Female	65 (43.3%)
Gamers vs non-Gamers	
Gamers	122 (81.3%)
Non-Gamers	28 (18.6%)
Gaming platform	
Mobile	108 (72%)
PC	10 (6.6%)
Gaming consoles (Non-gamers)	4 (2.6%) 28 (18.6%)
Most popular games	
PUBG	40 (26.6%)
Candy Crush Saga	35 (23.3%)
Subway Surfers	27 (18%)
Others (non-gamers)	20 (13.3%) 28 (18.6%)
Gaming frequency per week	
Never	28 (18.6%)
1–3 times/week	63 (42%)
4–5 times/week	23 (15.3%)
Almost Everyday	36 (24%)
Gaming duration (hours) per day	
0 (Non-gamers)	28 (18.6%)
<2 hrs	105 (70%)
2–6 hrs	15 (10%)
>6 hrs	2 (1.3%)
Single vs Multiplayer	
Single	81 (54%)
Multiplayer (Non-gamers)	41 (27.3%) 28 (18.6%)
With Internet gaming disorder without internet gaming disorder	
6%	94%

Table 2
 Pearson correlation between IGD score and SDQ total score with its domain subscales

	Total IGD score	Prosocial	Peer problems	Hyperactivity	Conduct problems	Emotional symptoms	Total SDQ score
Pearson Correlation	1	-.191*	.349**	-.051	.322**	.270**	.361**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.019	<.001	.533	<.001	<.001	<.001
N	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Pearson Correlation	-.191*	1	-.157	.117	-.152	.077	-.005
Sig. (2-tailed)	.019		.055	.155	.063	.349	.953
N	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Pearson Correlation	.349**	-.157	1	.359**	.418**	.448**	.662**
Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	.055		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
N	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Pearson Correlation	-.051	.117	.359**	1	.243**	.301**	.416**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.533	.155	<.001		.003	<.001	<.001
N	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Pearson Correlation	.322**	-.152	.418**	.243**	1	.321**	.568**
Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	.063	<.001	.003		<.001	<.001
N	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Pearson Correlation	.270**	.077	.448**	.301**	.321**	1	.607**
Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	.349	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
N	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
Pearson Correlation	.361**	-.005	.662**	.416**	.568**	.607**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	.953	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
N	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)
 ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 3
 Comparison of participants with and without Internet Gaming Disorder

Variable	Median (No IGD)	Mean ± SD (No IGD)	Median (With IGD)	Mean ± SD (With IGD)	Mann–Whitney <i>U</i> , <i>z</i> , <i>p</i> -value
Prosocial	8	7.10 ± 2.48	7	6.11 ± 3.29	<i>U</i> = 747, <i>z</i> = 0.8955, <i>p</i> = 0.003*
Peer Problems	3	3.10 ± 2.05	5	4.55 ± 2.18	<i>U</i> = 397, <i>z</i> = -1.89, <i>p</i> = 0.05
Hyperactivity	5	4.88 ± 2.28	3	3.77 ± 2.63	<i>U</i> = 1321.5, <i>z</i> = -1.87, <i>p</i> = 0.06
Conduct Problems	3	3.03 ± 2.24	4	3.77 ± 2.77	<i>U</i> = 530, <i>z</i> = -0.83, <i>p</i> < 0.01*
Emotional Symptoms	3	3.58 ± 2.59	6	5.66 ± 2.00	<i>U</i> = 321, <i>z</i> = -2.49, <i>p</i> < 0.01*
Total SDQ	23	23.3 ± 8.30	29	28.3 ± 6.70	<i>U</i> = 409, <i>z</i> = -1.77, <i>p</i> < 0.01*

**p* < 0.01

DISCUSSION

The study examined gaming trends and their psychological impact among adolescents and young adults in India, focusing on the correlation between Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD) scores and psychological variables measured through the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ). The findings provide insight into the prevalence of problematic gaming and its association with emotional symptoms, peer relationships, conduct problems, and social functioning.

The study sample consisted of 150 participants, with 56.6% male and 43.3% female, most of who were between 20 and 26 years old. A significant proportion (81%) identified as gamers, with mobile gaming being the most popular platform (72%), while gaming consoles such as PlayStation and Xbox were the least used (2.6%). These findings align with previous research on Indian adolescents, which similarly reported a high preference for mobile gaming, likely influenced by accessibility and affordability. Regarding gaming frequency, 24% of participants reported playing almost every day, while 42% played one to three times per week. Most participants (70%) played for less than two hours per session, whereas a smaller proportion (10%) played for two to six hours, and only 1.3% exceeded six hours per session. These patterns are consistent with global trends, including studies conducted in Sweden, where the majority of adolescent gamers reported playing for under two hours per day. The types of games played also varied, with PUBG (26.6%), Candy Crush Saga (23.3%), and Subway Surfers (18%) being the most popular.

Among the 150 participants, only 6% met the criteria for Internet Gaming Disorder, while 94% did not exhibit signs of problematic gaming. This aligns with global prevalence studies, such as research conducted in Russia, which estimated IGD prevalence at 1.3% among adolescents. While the overall prevalence of IGD in this study remains relatively low, the psychological implications for those classified as having problematic gaming behaviour warrant further examination.

The study assessed correlations between IGD scores and SDQ subscales, including emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity, peer problems, and pro-social behaviour. The results demonstrated significant correlations at the 0.01 level for most psychological variables, particularly peer problems, conduct problems, and emotional symptoms. Notably, pro-social behaviour was negatively correlated with IGD, while hyperactivity did not show a significant association. These findings suggest that problematic gaming behaviour is linked to emotional and behavioural difficulties but not necessarily to hyperactivity.

The total SDQ score exhibited a moderate positive correlation with IGD, indicating that individuals with higher IGD scores tend to experience greater psychological distress. The negative correlation with pro-social behaviour suggests that individuals with higher IGD scores exhibit slightly lower levels of social engagement. A moderate positive correlation was found between IGD scores and peer problems, implying that individuals with problematic gaming behaviour often experience

greater difficulties in peer relationships. Similarly, conduct problems were moderately associated with IGD; reinforcing concerns that problematic gaming may contribute to behavioural misconduct. A weak positive correlation was observed between IGD and emotional symptoms, suggesting that excessive gaming may impact emotional well-being. However, hyperactivity did not show a significant correlation with IGD, a finding that contrasts with some prior studies that have suggested a link between excessive gaming and attention-related issues. To further examine psychological differences, a Mann-Whitney U-test was conducted, revealing significant differences in multiple domains. Participants with IGD scored higher on the total SDQ scale, indicating greater overall psychological distress. Significant differences were also observed in emotional symptoms, peer problems, and conduct problems, where IGD participants exhibited greater difficulties compared to non-IGD individuals. Notably, IGD participants demonstrated lower pro-social behaviour, further reinforcing concerns about the social consequences of problematic gaming. However, no significant difference was observed in hyperactivity between the two groups.

These findings are consistent with previous research on IGD and adolescent mental health. Studies conducted in China and Italy has similarly shown that individuals with problematic gaming behaviour often experience emotional and behavioural difficulties. Additionally, research on Pakistani adolescents has highlighted how excessive gaming contributes to social withdrawal, antisocial tendencies, and difficulties in emotional regulation. While the current study aligns with these broader findings, the lack of significant correlation between hyperactivity and IGD suggests potential cultural or contextual differences that warrant further investigation. The results contribute to the ongoing discussion regarding the classification of IGD as a mental health condition. The observed correlations between problematic gaming and emotional, behavioural, and peer-related difficulties provide empirical support for its inclusion in psychiatric frameworks such as the DSM-5. However, the study also underscores the need for further research to refine diagnostic criteria and distinguish between problematic and recreational gaming.

With the continued growth of the online gaming industry, raising awareness about the potential risks of excessive gaming is essential. Schools, universities, and mental health professionals should implement preventative strategies, including education on responsible gaming habits, parenting interventions, and mental health support programs to help individuals at risk of developing IGD. Additionally, mental health initiatives such as counselling services, self-help groups, and structured intervention programs could play a critical role in mitigating the negative psychological effects associated with problematic gaming.

Overall, the study highlights important psychological correlations associated with problematic gaming while providing insights into gaming behaviour trends in the Indian adolescent population. The findings suggest that excessive gaming may negatively impact emotional well-being, peer relationships, and conduct. However, the relatively low prevalence of IGD in this study suggests that not all gaming behaviour is inherently problematic. Future research should explore additional socio-cultural and psychological factors influencing gaming addiction, with an emphasis on preventive measures and early intervention strategies to address potential mental health concerns.

LIMITATION

This study employed a convenience-based sampling method, which may introduce bias due to the non-random selection of participants. Consequently, the findings may not be fully generalisable to broader populations, as the sample may lack demographic diversity. Future research should aim for randomised or stratified sampling to enhance representativeness. The study relied on self-report measures for assessing gaming patterns and psychological variables, which may be subject to social

desirability bias or inaccuracies in self-perception. Incorporating clinician-based assessments or objective behavioural measures could provide a more comprehensive evaluation of gaming-related psychopathology. Additionally, while the study explored psychological correlates of gaming disorder, it did not account for other potential influencing factors, such as family dynamics, personality traits, or socio-economic status, which may contribute to problematic gaming behaviour. Future studies should adopt a multifactorial approach to better understand the underlying mechanisms.

The small proportion of participants ($n = 9$) who met the criteria for Internet Gaming Disorder limits the statistical power of group comparisons. A larger sample of individuals classified as at risk for gaming disorder is needed to improve the validity of findings. Another limitation relates to the measurement tool used. The study employed the DSM-5-based Internet Gaming Disorder Scale (IGDS9-SF), which conceptualises gaming disorder similarly to substance use disorders. Some researchers argue that this pathologises normal gaming behaviour and may lead to an overestimation of problematic gaming cases. Future research should explore alternative diagnostic frameworks to assess gaming disorder more accurately. This study focused on adolescents and young adults, limiting the generalisability of findings to other age groups. Future research should examine gaming disorder across different developmental stages to assess potential age-related differences in psychological impact.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between Internet Gaming Disorder (IGD) and psychological well-being among adolescents and young adults. The findings indicate that problematic gaming behaviour is significantly associated with emotional difficulties, peer relationship issues, and conduct problems, reinforcing concerns about the psychological impact of excessive gaming. The results align with existing literature suggesting that problematic gaming can contribute to mental health challenges, particularly in adolescence – a crucial developmental stage for emotional and social growth.

Given the increasing prevalence of gaming among young people, raising awareness about the potential risks of excessive gaming is essential. Schools, universities, and mental health professionals should implement preventative strategies, including education on responsible gaming habits, parenting interventions, and mental health support programs to help individuals at risk of developing IGD. Furthermore, mental health initiatives such as counselling services, self-help groups, and structured intervention programmes could play a critical role in mitigating the negative psychological effects associated with problematic gaming.

Future research should prioritise larger, more diverse sample sizes to improve the generalisability of findings. Additionally, incorporating qualitative research methods would offer deeper insights into the subjective experiences of problematic gamers, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how IGD manifests in different cultural and socioeconomic contexts. Longitudinal studies are also necessary to track long-term psychological outcomes associated with excessive gaming.

Finally, the findings highlight the importance of early intervention and tailored mental health support for adolescents engaged in gaming. With the rapid expansion of online gaming platforms, it is imperative that researchers, clinicians, and policymakers work together to develop evidence-based strategies to balance the benefits of gaming with potential risks. Addressing these challenges will help ensure that gaming remains a healthy and recreational activity rather than a source of psychological distress.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: JAIN University

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